

PHYTOSOMES: NOVEL APPROACH IN HERBAL MEDICINES

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*Received: 27 Jan 2012; Revised: 24 Feb.. 2012; Accepted: 22 Mar... 2012 Available online: 5 Apr 2012***ABSTRACT**

In recent times the emerging technology of drug delivery and drug targeting is also being applied to phytopharmaceuticals. Botanicals have enormous therapeutic potential which should be explored through some value added drug delivery systems. Phytosomes are recently introduced herbal formulations that are better absorbed, and as a result produce better bioavailability and actions than the conventional phytomolecules or botanical extracts. The term “Phyto” means plant while “some” means cell-like. It is also often known as herbosomes. Phytosomes are produced by a process whereby the standardized plant extract or its constituents are bound to phospholipids, mainly phosphatidylcholine producing a lipid compatible molecular complex. This phyto-phospholipid complex, phytosome resembles a little cell. Phytosomes exhibit better pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic profile than conventional herbal extracts. The phytosome technology has been effectively enhanced the bioavailability of many popular herbal extracts including milk thistle, Ginkgo biloba, grape seed, green tea, hawthorn, ginseng etc. and can be developed for various therapeutic uses or as dietary supplements. These drug-phospholipid complexes can be formulated in the form of solution, suspension, emulsion, syrup, lotion, gel, cream, aqueous micro dispersion, pill, capsule, powder, granules and chewable tablet.

Key words: Bioavailability, Herbal extracts, Phosphatidylcholine, Phospholipid complex, Phytosomes.

INTRODUCTION

Most of the herbal drug bioactive constituents are water soluble molecules. Phytosomes have improved pharmacokinetic and pharmacological parameters, which in result can advantageously be used in the treatment of acute and chronic liver disease of toxic metabolic or infective origin or of degenerative nature. Phytosomes are advanced herbal products produced by binding individual component of herbal extract to phytolipid mainly phosphatidylcholine resulting in a product that is better absorbed and produces better results than the conventional herbal extract. This technology is also useful in pharmaceutical formulations intended for treatment of oral cavity in which the contact times are very short because phospholipid allows a greater adhesion of the product itself to the surfaces it comes into contact with and so vastly improve their

absorption and bioavailability^[5]. The Phytosomes process produces a little cell because of that the valuable components of the herbal extract are protected from destruction by digestive secretions and gut bacteria. Phytosomes are better able to transition from a hydrophilic environment into the lipid-friendly environment of the enterocyte cell membrane and from there into the cell finally reaching the blood^[3]. It can also be used in anti-inflammatory activity as well as in pharmaceutical and cosmetic compositions^[5].

Preparation of Phytosomes:

Phytosomes are novel complexes which are prepared by reacting a natural or synthetic phospholipid, such as phosphatidylcholine, phosphatidylethanolamine or phosphatidylserine with polyphenolic component like simple flavonoids, either alone or in the natural mixture in aprotic solvent such as- dioxane or acetone from which complex can be isolated by precipitation with non solvent such as aliphatic hydrocarbons or lyophilization or by spray drying. In the complex formation of phytosomes the ratio between these two moieties is in the range from 0.5-2.0 moles. The most preferable ratio of phospholipid to flavonoids is 1:1. In the phytosome preparations, phospholipids are selected from the group consisting of soy lecithin, from bovine or swine brain or dermis, phosphatidylcholine, phosphatidylethanolamine, phosphatidylserine in which acyl group may be same or different and mostly derived from palmitic, stearic, oleic and linoleic acid. Selection of flavonoids are done from the group consisting of quercetin, kaempferol, quercetin-3, rhamnoglucoside, quercetin-3- rhamnoside, hyperoside, vitexine, diosmine, 3- rhamnoside, (+) catechin, (-) epicatechin, apigenin-7-glucoside, luteolin, luteolinglucoside, ginkgonetine, isoginkgonetine and bilobetine. On the basis of their physical-chemical and spectroscopic characteristics, these complexes can be considered as novel entities^[7, 8]. Phosphatidylcholine is a bifunctional compound, the phosphatidyl moiety being lipophilic and the choline moiety being hydrophilic in nature. Specifically the choline head of the phosphatidylcholine molecule binds to these compounds while the lipid soluble phosphatidyl portion comprising the body and tail which then envelopes the choline bound material. Hence, the phytoconstituents produce a lipid compatible molecular complex with phospholipids, also called as phyto-phospholipid complex. Molecules are anchored through chemical bonds to the polar choline head of the phospholipids, as can be demonstrated by specific spectroscopic techniques^[7, 8, 9].

Difference between Phytosome and Liposome-

Likewise phytosomes, a liposome is formed by mixing a water soluble substance with phosphatidylcholine in definite ratio under specific conditions. Here, no chemical bond is

formed; the phosphatidylcholine molecules surround the water soluble substance. There may be hundreds or even thousands of phosphatidylcholine molecules surrounding the water-soluble compound. In contrast, with the phytosome process the phosphatidylcholine and the plant components actually form a 1:1 or 2:1 molecular complex depending on the substance(s) complexes, involving chemical bonds. This difference results in phytosome being much better absorbed than liposomes showing better bioavailability. Phytosomes have also been found superior to liposomes in topical and skin care products ^[9] (Fig. 1).

Fig.1

Fig. 1: Shows difference between liposome and phytosome.

The molecular organization of the liposome (upper segment)

The molecular organization of phytosomes (lower segment)

Properties of Phytosomes:

1. Physico Chemical properties:

Phytosomes is a complex between a natural product and natural phospholipids, like soy phospholipids. Such a complex is obtained by reaction of stoichiometric amounts of phospholipids and the substrate in an appropriate solvent. On the basis of spectroscopic data it has been shown that the main phospholipid-substrate interaction is due to the formation of

hydrogen bonds between the polar head of phospholipids (i.e. phosphate and ammonium groups) and the polar functionalities of the substrate. When treated with water, phytosomes assumes a micellar shape forming liposomal structure ^[11].

2. Biological properties:

Phytosomes are advanced forms of herbal products that are better absorbed, utilized and as a result produce better results than conventional herbal extracts. The increased bioavailability of the phytosome over the non complexed botanical derivatives has been demonstrated by pharmacokinetic studies or by pharmacodynamic tests in experimental animals and in human subjects ^[11].

Characterization of Phytosomes:

The behaviour of phytosomes in both physical and biological system is governed by the factors such as physical size, membrane permeability, and percentage of entrapped solutes, chemical composition as well as the quantity and purity of the starting materials. Therefore, the phytosomes are characterized for physical attributes i.e. shape, size, its distribution, percentage drug capture, entrapped volume, percentage drug release and chemical composition ^[12].

Mechanism of phytophospholipids complex formation:

The poor absorption of flavonoid nutrients is likely due to two main factors. First, these are multiple ring molecules not quite small enough to be absorbed from the intestine into the blood by simple diffusion, nor does the intestinal lining actively absorb them, as occurs with some vitamins and minerals. Second, flavonoid molecules typically have poor miscibility with oils and others lipids. This severely limits their ability to pass across the lipid-rich outer membranes of the enterocytes, the cells that line the small intestine. The phytosomes technology meets this challenge. Phytosomes results from the reaction of a stoichiometric amount of the phospholipid (phosphatidylcholine) with the standardized extract or polyphenolic constituents (like simple flavonoids) in a non polar solvent. Phytosomes also have been found superior to liposomes in topical and skin care products ^[18].

Advantages of Phytosomes:

As compared to conventional herbal formulation, Phytosomes have following advantages-

It enhances the absorption of lipid insoluble polar phytoconstituents through oral as well as topical route showing better bioavailability, hence significantly greater therapeutic benefit.

As the absorption of active constituent(s) is improved, its dose requirement is also reduced.

Phosphatidylcholine used in preparation of phytosomes, besides acting as a carrier also acts as a hepatoprotective, hence giving the synergistic effect when hepatoprotective substances are employed.

Chemical bonds are formed between phosphatidylcholine molecule and phytoconstituent, so the phytosomes show better stability profile.

Added nutritional benefit of phospholipids.

Appreciable drug entrapment.

Application of phytoconstituents in form of phytosome improves their percutaneous absorption and act as functional cosmetics.

Phytosome process produces a little cell whereby the valuable components of the herbal extracts are protected from destruction by digestive secretions and gut bacteria.

Assured delivery to the tissues.

Phosphatidylcholine used in the phytosome process besides acting as a carrier also nourishes the skin, because it is essential part of cell membrane.

Phytosomes are also superior to liposomes in skin care products.

Significantly greater clinical benefit.

The particular structure of phytosome elicits peculiar properties and advantages in cosmetic application.

Enhanced ability of phytosomes to cross cell membranes and enter cells.

Their low solubility in aqueous media allows the formation of stable emulsions or creams

Evaluation of Phytosomes:

Various spectroscopic and in-vitro and in-vivo evaluations are applied on phytosomes. These complexes can be characterized by Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM), ¹H-NMR, ¹³C-NMR, ³¹P-NMR and FT-IR. Models of in-vitro and in-vivo evaluations are selected on the basis of expected therapeutic activity of biologically active phytoconstituents present in Phytosomes. Complexation increases the activity of the active principle. A chemical spectral characteristic is determined in phospholipids complexes using IR and UV spectroscopic study. Liquid chromatography/atmospheric pressure chemical ionization mass spectrometry (LC/APCI-ITMS) proved to be a very powerful tool for pharmacokinetic studies of phytochemicals. The effects of Ginkgo biloba dimeric flavonoids in Phytosomes form on the vasomotor activity and skin microcirculation of the cheeks, hands, limbs and female breast are studied in human subjects by Infrared-Photo-Pulse-Plethysmography, Laser Doppler Flowmetry, High Performance Contact Thermography, Computerized Video thermography, and Optic Probe Video capillaroscopy. In-

vivo studies are performed on Beagle dogs, rodents, wistar rats to compare pharmacokinetics parameters between pure extracts and its phospholipid complex [15, 16, 17].

Applications of Phytosomes:

Most of the phytosomal studies are focused to *Silybum marianum* which contains premier liver-protectant flavonoids. The fruit of the milk thistle plant (*S. marianum*, Family Steraceae) contains flavonoids known for hepatoprotective effects. Silymarin has been shown to have positive effects in treating liver diseases of various kinds, including hepatitis, cirrhosis, fatty infiltration of the liver (chemical and alcohol induced fatty liver) and inflammation of the bile duct. Francesco *et al.*, (2009) studied on a recently developed oral formulation in the form of coated tablets containing highly bioavailable green tea extract (GreenSelect® Phytosome) which was tested in obese subjects of both genders on a hypocaloric diet. After 90 days of treatment, significant weight loss and decreased body mass index (BMI) were observed in the group taking the herbal extract. Phytosomes are advanced form of herbal extract that are better absorbed which results better than conventional herbal extract. Phytosomes have improved pharmacokinetic and pharmacological parameter, which in result can advantageously be used in treatment of acute liver diseases, either metabolic or infective origin. Absorption of phytosome in gastro-intestinal tract is appreciably greater resulting in increased plasma level than the individual component. Green tea has got several long term beneficial activities such as antioxidant, anticarcinogenic, antimutagenic, antiatherosclerotic, hypocholesterolemic, cardio-protective, anti-bacterial and anti-cariogenic effects. Hence, the therapeutic action becomes enhanced, more detectable and prolonged. In this way after screening and selection of potential extracts or constituents from plants, phytosomes can be developed for different therapeutic purposes like cardiovascular, antiinflammatory, immunomodulator, anticancer, antidiabetic etc or fo prophylactic and health purposes as nutraceuticals, in due course[17,18].

CONCLUSION:

Phytosomes are novel compounds comprising of lipophilic complexes of components of various plants like *Silybum Marianum*, *Ginkgo Biloba*, *ginseng* etc with phospholipids. Preparation of phytosomes is usually carried out by non conventional method. Absorption of phytosome in gastro intestinal tract is appreciably greater resulting in increased plasma level than the individual component. Complex formation ratio of component and phospholipids is 1:1 and 2:1. Phytosomes are used as a medicament and have wide scope in cosmeticology. Many areas of phytosome are to be revealed in future in the prospect of pharmaceutical application. Phytosomes forms a bridge between the conventional delivery system and novel delivery system. Phytosomes

enables pharmaceutical manufacturers to provide new pharmaceutical products using water soluble drugs and provides new developments in medical industry. The technology can effectively deliver the product by topical and oral route.

Table 1: Commercial Phytosome Products ^[9, 10, 12]

Phytosomes	Phytoconstituents complexed	Indications
Silybin Phytosome TM	Silybin from <i>Silybum marianum</i>	Hepatoprotective, antioxidant for liver and skin
Ginkgo Phytosome TM	Ginkgo flavonoids from <i>Ginkgo biloba</i>	Protects brain and vascular linings, anti skin ageing
Ginseng Phytosome TM	Ginsenosides from <i>Panax ginseng</i>	Nutraceutical, immunomodulator
Green Tea Phytosome TM	Epigallocatechin from <i>Thea sinensis</i>	Nutraceutical, systemic antioxidant, anticancer
Grape Seed Phytosome TM	Procyanidins from <i>Vitis vinifera</i>	Nutraceutical, systemic antioxidant, cardioprotective
Hawthorn Phytosome TM	Flavonoids from <i>Crataegus sp.</i>	Nutraceutical, cardio-protective and Antihypertensive
Olive oil Phytosome	Polyphenols from <i>Olea europaea</i> oil	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-hyperlipidemic
Echinacea Phytosome	Echinacosides from <i>Echinacea augustifolia</i>	Nutraceutical, immunomodulator
Centella Phytosome	Terpenes	Vein and Skin disorders
Palmetto berries Phytosomes	fatty acids, alcohols and sterols	Non-cancerous prostate enlargement.
Super Milk thistle Extract	Silybin from Silymarin Food Product	antioxidant for liver and skin
Bilberry Phytosomes	extract of bilberry which provides Anthocyanosides	Improve capillary tone, reduce abnormal blood vessel permeability, and are potent antioxidants

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Marketed preparations:

